

D4.6 VERIFICATION OF BARRIER CONCEPT FOR THE FINAL DEMONSTRATOR WORK PACKAGE 4

Associated Task(s):

Task 4.5: Evaluation of barrier concepts

Task 4.2: Characterization of input material,
benchmarking of cleaning processes

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PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present Deliverable combines results previously presented in public deliverables D4.3 “Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes” and D4.2 “Evaluation of barrier concepts” in order to evaluate the potential transfer of substances from the 100% Project PE PCR (polyethylene-based layer composed entirely of post-consumer recyclate) integrated in the designed laminate structure, according to current legislative requirements.

Taking into account the barrier properties (mainly barrier improvement factors, BIF) of various functional barrier layers (see D4.2), the identification and (semi-)quantification of components of the 100 % Project PE PCR (from Loop3 Cycle1) (see D4.3), and performed calculations on the potential concentrations in food, it was shown that developed laminate structure of CIRCULAR FoodPack has the potential to reduce migration of undesired substances below the threshold levels of toxicological concern.

The results and the above conclusion are based on experimental analysis of functional barrier layers produced under defined conditions at a (small) technical scale, however, they are based on only a single production lot. It is recommended to establish the BIF for barrier layers / structures produced at commercial scale and thus statistically validate the BIF values. It should also be noted that the thickness of individual layers (e.g., EVOH) has a significant influence on the overall barrier performance. To ensure long-term effectiveness, the functional barrier(s) must be verified as intact within the laminate structure, thereby meeting the criteria of a functional barrier.

For the assessment, the monofilm made of 100 % PE PCR from Loop3 Cycle 1 was characterized with respect to identity and content of migratable components. It is recommended to perform analytical controls of input materials and output recyclates to gain further insights and statistical data on the presence of undesired contaminants. This is in line with the requirements and quality control aspects set out by Regulation No 2022/1616.

As an overall conclusion, only the combination of high-quality PE PCR material with functional barrier(s) will be capable to reduce migration of undesired substances below the threshold levels of toxicological concern.

Poor qualities of PE PCR (such as the investigated commercial waste fractions, without any further decontamination treatment) will not qualify – even if used behind functional barriers – to be used in sensitive packaging applications.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
BIF	Barrier improvement factor
BfR	Bundesinstitut für Risikobewertung
CAD	Charged aerosol detector
CMR	Substances classified as carcinogenic, mutagenic, or toxic for reproduction
D	Deliverable
EU	European Union
EVOH	Ethylene vinyl alcohol
FCM	Food contact material
FID	Flame ionization detection
GC	Gas chromatography
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
HRMS	High resolution mass spectrometry
MDOPE	Machine direction orientation polyethylene
MS	Mass spectrometry
PAA	Primary aromatic amine
PCR	Post-consumer recyclates
PE	Polyethylene
SiO _x	Silicon oxide
SML	Specific migration limit
WP	Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of work package (WP) 4 is to define, evaluate and assess innovative recycling strategies and newly developed packaging structures for the use of post-consumer recycled polyethylene (PE PCR) in flexible packaging for food and personal care applications. For this purpose, analytical migration and compliance testing was applied in order to assess and ensure food regulatory compliance of the laminate structures developed within this project.

Within Task 4.5 (see public deliverable D4.2) laminate structures were investigated and characterized for their barrier properties by means of permeation measurements. The most efficient combinations were proposed to WP5 for further selection within the definition of a final packaging structure (for food packaging and personal care applications).

In addition, the barrier's efficiency and capability to reduce the transfer of undesired contaminants into packed food strongly depends on the level of residual contaminants present in the final materials and articles. This aspect was addressed in Task 4.2 (see public deliverable D4.3), where the chromatographic fingerprint of various recyclates was characterized by analytical screening techniques (such as Headspace GC-MS, GC-FID/MS with liquid injection, HPLC-HRMS/CAD) including the (semi-)quantification of residual contents.

The present Deliverable combines results as already presented in D4.3 "Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes" and D4.2 "Evaluation of barrier concepts" in order to evaluate the potential transfer of substances from the 100 % Project PE PCR in the designed laminate structure taking into account current legislative requirements.

2. DISCUSSION

a. Laminate structure

The final structure of the laminate for loop 3 (flexible food packaging) was designed as follows:

Loop 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1):

MDOPE/primer/SiOx/printed/adhesive/PE PCR L3C1/adhesive/ PE/EVOH/PE

	27.5 µm MDOPE (virgin), coated with Primer + SiOx
	6.5 µm printing ink + adhesive
	54 µm PE PCR film (mixture of L3C1 PCR + commercial PCR)
	1.5 µm adhesive
	37.2 µm coextruded film of PE/EVOH/PE (virgin) EVOH layer thickness = 2.5 µm

Figure 1: Final laminate structure for Loop 3 Cycle 1 (L3C1) with PE PCR

In this structure, the PE PCR film is sandwiched between **PE/EVOH/PE** as a barrier towards the inside (food contact side) of the package and MDOPE and **Primer + SiOx** towards the non-food contact side. The outside structure was designed in order to establish a barrier towards set-off, which can take place in case the laminate film is stored on a roll.

b. Calculation of migration values for exemplary migrants

Within task 4.5 (as reported in public deliverable D4.2) several structures / materials were analyzed for their barrier properties. The barrier types as given in Table 1 were selected and integrated into the final demonstrator laminate.

Table 1: Barrier structures developed within Task4.5 (D4.2) and considered for the migration calculations

Laminate ID	Barrier film type	Highest BIF	Lowest BIF ¹
CFP00101	with EVOH Coextrusion of PE and EVOH	6416 as determined for phenylcyclohexane	1512 as determined for benzophenone
CFP00104	with primer A and SiOx Combination of organic and inorganic coating	845 as determined for methylsalicylate	379 as determined benzophenone

¹ Taking into account physico-chemical properties and instrumental setup (vapor pressures, measurement conditions), the values (BIF) for methyl stearate from D4.2 are excluded for the barrier assessment.

Within task 4.5 a comprehensive evaluation of the barrier performance of various potential barrier layers (both organic and inorganic, as well as combinations) was performed (as presented in detail in the public deliverable D4.2). For this purpose, barrier films were prepared where the PE layer was contaminated with artificial surrogates. These different barrier films were subsequently subjected to permeation measurements. From the obtained data, barrier improvement factors (**BIF**) were calculated to characterize the effectiveness of the barrier layer towards the tested surrogates with different molecular weights and polarities. From the experiments, it was concluded that structure “PE/EVOH/PE” (CFP00101) showed the highest barrier effect towards the tested substances. For the combination of a “primer with SiOx” (CFP00104), the barrier performance was determined to be fairly efficient and slightly more efficient than the primer alone for the tested substances (please refer to D4.2 for the detailed measurement results).

In Task 4.2 (as reported in detail in public Deliverable D4.3 “Characterization of input material, benchmarking of cleaning processes”), the chromatographic fingerprint of various recyclates was characterized by analytical screening techniques (such as Headspace GC-MS, GC-FID/MS with liquid injection, HPLC-HRMS/CAD) including (semi-)quantification of residual contents. These experiments were used to set up a database in Task 4.4 (confidential deliverable D4.5 “Database of contaminants in recycled polyolefins”) on detected substances (identified and non-identified) and the respective concentrations in the material. The data for the 100 % project recyclate of Loop 3 Cycle 1 is used for the calculations and discussions in the present Deliverable. For this purpose, representative semi-volatile and non-volatile substances, detected and (semi-)quantified in this material by GC-FID/MS and LC-HRMS/CAD, were chosen from the following categories:

- Identified substance intentionally used in the production of polyolefins / safety assessment available
- Identified substance non-intentionally present in the material / safety assessment available
- Non-identified substance / unknown toxicological properties

Summary of underlying data basis and assumptions for the calculations

For the representatives out of these three categories of migratable chemical substances, the theoretical transfer onto food was calculated applying the (semi-)quantification results, the highest and lowest experimentally determined BIF, a surface-to-volume ratio of 6 dm² / kg according to the EU cube model and assuming total transfer. In addition, the calculations were performed assuming a PE PCR content of 30 % in the final package structure. The results are given in the following table.

Table 2: **Calculated migration values** for representative substances (originating from the project PE-PCR) for the developed demonstrator laminate which included two barrier structures **PE/EVOH/PE (barrier structure 1)** and **Primer + SiOx (barrier structure 2)**

Substance	Comment / Analysis	Concentration	Area related migration potential*	Migration into food **	Migration corr.*** Structure 1 BIF 1	Migration corr.*** Structure 1 BIF 2	Migration corr.*** Structure 2 BIF 1	Migration corr.*** Structure 2 BIF 2	30 % PCR Structure 1 BIF 1	30 % PCR Structure 1 BIF 2	30 % PCR Structure 2 BIF 1	30 % PCR Structure 2 BIF 2
		[µg/g material]	[µg/dm ²]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]	[µg/kg food]
2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CAS 96-76-4)	typical additive degradation product; GC-FID/MS	5	2,7	16,1	0,003	0,011	0,019	0,043	0,001	0,003	0,006	0,013
7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro (4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione (CAS 82304-66-3)	typical additive degradation product; GC-FID/MS	4	1,8	10,8	0,002	0,007	0,013	0,028	0,001	0,002	0,004	0,009
Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite / Irgafos 168 (CAS 31570-04-4)	representative PE additive; GC-FID/MS	1402	701	4207	0,656	2,782	4,979	11,100	0,197	0,835	1,494	3,330
Di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (DEHP) (CAS 117-81-7)	plasticizer; GC-FID/MS	1	0,4	2,6	0,000	0,002	0,003	0,007	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,002
<i>Not-identified substance low concentration</i>	GC-FID/MS	1	0,5	3,0	0,000	0,002	0,004	0,008	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,002
<i>Not-identified substance highest concentration</i>	GC-FID/MS	14	6,8	40,9	0,006	0,027	0,048	0,108	0,002	0,008	0,015	0,032
Octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4- hydroxyphenyl)propionate (CAS 2082-79-3)	representative PE additive; LC-HRMS/CAD	71	35	212	0,033	0,140	0,251	0,559	0,010	0,042	0,075	0,168
4,4'-methylene dianiline (CAS 101-77-9)	PAA; LC-HRMS/CAD	15	7,7	45,9	0,007	0,030	0,054	0,121	0,002	0,009	0,016	0,036
<i>Not-identified substance low concentration</i>	LC-HRMS/CAD	1	0,5	3,0	0,000	0,002	0,004	0,008	0,000	0,001	0,001	0,002
<i>Not-identified substance highest concentration</i>	LC-HRMS/CAD	54	27,2	162,9	0,025	0,108	0,193	0,430	0,008	0,032	0,058	0,129

*: with an area weight of approx. 0.5 g/dm²

** : with a surface-to-volume area of 6 dm² according to the EU cube mode and assuming total transfer without any barrier

***: migration value considering the barrier improvement factors

Structure 1 (CFP00101; PE/EVOH/PE) BIF 1 calculated with the highest BIF as determined for phenylcyclohexane and **BIF 2** calculated with the lowest BIF as determined for benzophenone

Structure 2 (CFP00104; Primer + SiOx) BIF 1 calculated with the highest BIF as determined for methylsalicylate and **BIF 2** calculated with the lowest BIF as determined for benzophenone

c. Food regulatory background

Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 aims at ensuring the chemical and microbiological safety of recycled plastic intended to come into contact with food, including food packaging ('recycled plastic FCMs'). It sets out specific rules that become directly applicable to the placing on the market of plastic with recycled content, including the collection and sorting of the plastic input, its decontamination, and conversion, affecting also quality control, documentation and labelling². All kinds of recycled plastic and recycling technologies are in the scope of the Regulation, including mechanical recycling, recycling of products from a closed and controlled product chain, the use of recycled plastic behind a functional barrier, and forms of chemical recycling.

In addition, the Regulation includes a procedure that establishes whether novel recycling technologies are suitable to recycle plastic FCMs. It supports the development of innovative recycling technologies that are likely to allow in the future the recycling of plastics that cannot be recycled today into FCMs, while it maintains a high level of safety of those recycled plastics.

Article 32 of Regulation (EU) 2022/1616 explicitly deals with the use of recycled plastics behind a functional barrier. Here, the functional barriers shall prevent migration to food of contaminants contained in the recycled plastic. As explained in recital clause (33), this technology [i.e. the functional barrier concept] cannot yet be established as a 'suitable recycling technology' from the legislator's point of view. However, unlike other technologies to be considered as novel for the purposes of this Regulation, the main principles of this technology are already understood. This allows to lay down specific adaptations to the rules on novel technologies concerning the use of a functional barrier until a decision is taken on its suitability, and in particular to add a requirement to verify the effectiveness of the barrier principle.

From the legislator's point of view, it does not appear necessary to require the monitoring of all these recycling installations in order to obtain sufficient data on contamination levels, but the ability of the functional barriers to prevent migration of contaminants on the long term must be guaranteed (e.g. by extensive reasoning, and scientific evidence and testing).

In principle, the barrier layers shall ensure that contaminants originating from the PCR layer remain below certain migration limits or levels of toxicological concern.

A limit value of 10 µg/kg is typically applied in the evaluation of *functional barriers* as laid down in the European Plastics Regulation (EU) No 10/2011. According to Art. 13 (2) of Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, non-authorized / non-identified substances may be used in multilayer material beyond the food contact layer, provided that the substances are not classified as mutagenic, carcinogenic or toxic for reproduction (CMR substances) according to the criteria of Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 and a transfer (migration) of these non-evaluated components into the food is not detectable at a detection limit of 0.01 mg/kg food simulant (10 µg/kg = 10 ppb).

As a conservative approach, potential contaminants in the recyclate are considered as genotoxic compounds due to the fact that some of the post-consumer substances cannot be identified by

² https://food.ec.europa.eu/safety/chemical-safety/food-contact-materials/plastic-recycling_en

instrumental analysis³. According to the Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC) approach, the threshold value for the oral uptake of genotoxic compounds is set at 0.15 µg/person/day⁴ for adults (or 0.0025 µg/kg body weight/day). Under the conventional assumption of a consumption of 1 kg of food per day, this corresponds to a concentration of 0.15 µg/kg (ppb) of the respective substance in food. It must be considered that for some populations such as infants this exposure threshold is lower due to a lower body weight.

For substances detected in the recycled material that are listed in the union list of authorized substances according to Regulation (EU) No 10/2011 or subject to an evaluation of national or international authorities, the respective migration limits or thresholds values can be applied.

d. Interpretation of results in the context of regulatory limits

In the following the three categories of potential migrants and underlying data basis and assumption (as described in section b) are discussed.

Identified substance intentionally used in the production of polyolefins / safety assessment available:

In the project recycle of Loop3 Cycle 1, tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl) phosphite (CAS 31570-04-4; trade name e.g. Irgafos 168) and octadecyl 3-(3,5-di-tert-butyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)propionate (CAS 2082-79-3; trade name e.g. Irganox 1076) were detected by GC-FID/MS analysis. Both substances are commonly used as antioxidants in food contact plastics and are authorized additives according to the Union list in Annex I of the Plastics Regulation (EU) No 10/2011. Irgafos 168 is listed without a specific migration limit (SML). Irganox 1076 is subject to a migration limit of 6 mg/kg food. For both barrier structures considered, the theoretical migration values were calculated to be below the specific migration limit for Irganox 1076.

As a further representative of an authorized substance, the plasticizer di(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate (CAS 117-81-7; DEHP) was evaluated. This substance is subject to a migration limit of 60 mg/kg food according to Regulation (EU) No 10/2011. The theoretical migration values as calculated for both structures are below this limit.

³ Scientific Opinion on the criteria to be used for safety evaluation of a mechanical recycling process to produce recycled PET intended to be used for manufacture of materials and articles in contact with food, EFSA Journal 2011;9(7):2184

⁴ Scientific Opinion on Exploring options for providing advice about possible human health risks based on the concept of Threshold of Toxicological Concern (TTC). EFSA Journal 2012;10(7):2750, 103 pp

Identified substance non-intentionally present in the material / safety assessment available:

2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CAS 96-76-4) and 7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione are low molecular weight compounds that are commonly reported in scientific literature as degradation products of antioxidants authorized for the use in food contact applications^{5,6,7}.

2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol (CAS 96-76-4) and 7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione were evaluated by the German BfR⁸ in drinking water on behalf of a request of the German Umweltbundesamt. 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol and 7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione correspond to substance Arvin 4 and Arvin 8. BfR proposed a drinking water positive list limit (DWPLL) of 25 µg/l for Arvin 4⁹. For Arvin 8, the German Umweltbundesamt derived a maximum tolerable concentration (MTC_{tap}) of 100 µg/l based on a 90-days feeding study¹⁰. An exposure of 2 l water per day is assumed and the value shall correspond only to 1/10 of the tolerable daily intake. Therefore a DWPLL / MTC_{tap} value can be derived from SML values for food contact materials by dividing by factor 20¹¹. In reverse conclusion, a DWPLL / MTC_{tap} value of 25 µg/l and 100 µg/l respectively, will correspond to a specific migration limit of 0.5 mg/kg food (simulant) for 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol and 2 mg/kg food (simulant) for 7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione. The theoretical migration values as calculated for both structures are below these limits.

4,4'-methylene dianiline (CAS 101-77-9) is a primary aromatic amine (PAA) that was detected in the 100 % PCR film (Loop3 Cycle1) using LC-HRMS/CAD. Potential sources for the formation or release of PAAs are azo colourants and other colour pigments as well as residual isocyanates used in PU-adhesives / other polyurethanes. PAAs are in the public focus because of their toxicological properties. According to the Plastics Regulation (EU) No 10/2011, primary aromatic amines listed in entry 43 to Appendix 8 of Annex XVII to Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006, such as 4,4'-methylene dianiline, shall not be released from plastic materials and articles into food or food simulant applying a limit of detection of 0.002 mg/kg food(simulant) for each individual primary aromatic amine. For both barrier structures considered, the theoretical migration value of 4,4'-methylene dianiline is below the limit of 0.002 mg/kg food(simulant).

⁵ I. Skjevraak, C. Brede, I.-L. Steffensen, A. Mikalsen, J. Alexander, P. Fjeldal, H. Herikstad, Non-targeted multi-component analytical surveillance of plastic food contact materials: Identification of substances not included in EU positive lists and their risk assessment; *Food Additives and Contaminants*, 2005, 22, 1012.

⁶ D. Löscher, T. Rapp, F.-U. Schlosser, R. Schuster, E. Stottmeister, S. Zander, Experience with the application of the draft European Standard prEN 15768 to the identification of leachable organic substances from materials in contact with drinking water by GC-MS, *Analytical Methods*, 2011, 3, 2547.

⁷ E. Reingruber, M. Himmelsbach, C. Sauer, W. Buchberger, Identification of degradation products of antioxidants in polyolefins by liquid chromatography combined with atmospheric pressure photoionisation mass spectrometry, *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2010, 95(5), 740-745.

⁸ 20. Sitzung der BfR-Kommission für Bedarfsgegenstände am 11. April 2018, Ergebnisprotokoll; www.bfr.bund.de

⁹ D. Brocca, E. Arvin, H. Mosbæk, Identification of organic compounds migrating from polyethylene pipelines into drinking water, *Water Research*, 2002, 36(15): 3675-3680.

¹⁰ 31. Sitzung der BfR-Kommission für Bedarfsgegenstände am 29. November 2023, Ergebnisprotokoll; <https://mobil.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/31-sitzung-der-bfr-kommission-fuer-bedarfsgegenstaende.pdf>

¹¹ Umwelt-Bundesamt, Bewertungsgrundlage für Kunststoffe und andere organische Materialien im Kontakt mit Trinkwasser, as of 23.08.2024

Non-identified substance / unknown toxicological properties:

Several substance peaks were detected in the sample material through GC and LC analysis that could not be identified via mass spectrometric detection. As an overall concentration range over the performed analyses, non-identified substances were (semi-)quantified with approx. 1 µg/g material up to approx. 55 µg/g. As a conservative approach, non-identified substances in the recyclate are considered as genotoxic compounds and consequently, the limit value of 0.15 µg/kg food(simulant) applies. It was calculated that a concentration of 65 µg/g in the material corresponds to a concentration of 0.15 µg/kg in the food based on the assumptions laid down for the calculations. The maximum concentration of 55 µg/g as determined for non-identified substances in the performed experiments consequently corresponds to a theoretical migration value below 0.15 µg/kg food(simulant) for both barrier structures considered.

3. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Taking into account the barrier properties (mainly barrier improvement factors, BIF) (see public deliverable D4.2), the identification and (semi-)quantification of components of the 100 % Project PE PCR (from Loop3 Cycle1) (see public deliverable D4.3), and performed calculations on the potential concentrations in food, it was shown that developed laminate structure of CIRCULAR FoodPack (as described in deliverables D6.3, D6.4, D6.5) has the potential to reduce migration of undesired substances below the threshold limits of toxicological concern.

The results and the above conclusion are based on experimental analysis of barrier layers produced under defined conditions at (small) technical scale, however they originate from only a single production lot. It is recommended to establish the BIF for barrier layers / structures produced at commercial scale and thus statistically validate the BIF values. It should also be noted that the thickness of individual layers (e.g., EVOH) has a significant influence on the overall barrier performance. To ensure long-term effectiveness, the functional barrier(s) must be verified as intact within the laminate structure, thereby meeting the criteria of a functional barrier.

For the assessment, the monofilm made of 100 % PE PCR from Loop3 Cycle1 was characterized with respect to identity and content of migratable components. It is recommended to perform analytical controls of input materials and output recyclates to gain further insights and statistical data on the presence of undesired contaminants. This is in line with the requirements and quality control aspects set out by Regulation No 2022/1616.

As an overall conclusion, only the combination of high-quality PE PCR material with functional barrier(s) will be capable to reduce migration of undesired substances below the threshold levels of toxicological concern.

Poor qualities of PE PCR (such as the investigated commercial waste fractions, without any further decontamination treatment) will not qualify – even if used behind functional barriers – to be used in sensitive packaging applications.

